

Join of 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) frags. 5 and 46

Eibert Tigchelaar, KU Leuven

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James R. Davila (1994) published as the manuscript 4Q1 or 4QGen-Exod^a an assemblage of fragments, preserving parts of Genesis 22 through Exodus 8 and written in the same hand, which earlier editors had brought together. In addition, he published twenty-three tiny unidentified fragments (4Q1 frags. 38-61) which had previously been assigned to or associated with 4Q1 on the basis of physical and palaeographic features. One of those unidentified fragments (4Q1 frag. 60) has been reassigned to 4Q49 (Tigchelaar, 2021). Another unidentified fragment (frag. 47) can be joined to 4Q1 frag. 47 (Tigchelaar, 2021a). I am not aware of other identifications of 4Q1 frags. 38-61.

The unidentified fragment 4Q1 frag. 46 joins materially and textually to 4Q1 frag at the right side of lines 15 and 16. These lines may now be transcribed as follows (frag. 46 in red):

ב[אֲרִץ כְּנָעַן וַיִּקַּח עָשׂוּ אֶת נְשָׂיו וְאֵת בְּנֵיו וְאֵת	15
קְנִי]נֹו אֲשֶׁר רָכַשׁ בְּאֶרֶץ כְּנָעַן [וַיֵּלֶךְ אֶל]	16

It is impossible to reconstruct here the full lines since, as recognized by Davila (p. 13), there is not enough room between the end of line 15 and the beginning of line 16 to accommodate all of the Masoretic text. Davila assume some of the text has been lost by haplography.

4Q1 frag. 5 (lines 14-20) + frag. 46 joined with Gimp; images taken from <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284249> <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284246> photographs PAM 43.006 and 43.009 taken by Najib Anton Albina

James R. Davila (1994) "1. 4QGen-Exod^a," in *Qumran Cave 4 VII: Genesis to Numbers*, ed. Eugene Ulrich and Frank Moore Cross; Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XII (Oxford: Clarendon Press)

Eibert Tigchelaar (2021) "4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) Frag. 60 + 4Q49 (4QJudg^a)." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5114482>

Eibert Tigchelaar (2021a) "Join of 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) frags. 9 and 47." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5525212>